

***METHODOLOGY OF EDUCATION OF CHILDREN WITH HEARING
DEFECTS***

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Introduction: The branch of special pedagogy is deaf pedagogy (Lat. "surdus"-deafness), a science that studies the development of hearing-impaired children and adults, and the laws of their education (the branch of special pedagogy). The development of hearing-impaired children of primary and preschool age, the processes and laws of their education is the subject of preschool deaf pedagogy. The pre-school period is important in the development of a child with a hearing impairment, because the early initiation of corrective and pedagogical measures helps to prevent deficiencies in the child's growth, as well as to educate a socially active, well-rounded person. The study of pre-school deaf pedagogy as a separate discipline is determined by the presence of physical, mental and physiological characteristics of children with hearing impairment, the need to take these factors into account when organizing children's lives and creating favorable educational and educational conditions.

Developmental characteristics and possibilities of hearing impaired children are determined based on the need to provide them with corrective and pedagogical support from the first period. A decrease in hearing ability has a negative impact on the general and mental development of a child, most importantly on the formation of speech. A deaf and hard-of-hearing child cannot speak unless specially trained, and uses a limited number of gestures in dealing with others. Imitating adults in their daily life, children can perform simple practical activities, master the functional tasks of various objects and use them correctly, acquire the skills of self-service. In the absence of special educational conditions for such children, their sensory and mental development is not influenced by spoken speech due to the fact that they cannot perceive the speech of others. Thus, although the child's development does not stop due to hearing loss and impaired speech development, it is much more limited.

Therefore, in order for children to develop as described in the brochure, it is necessary to create more special educational and educational conditions than children with normal hearing. By providing special education to children with hearing impairment from an early age, it will be possible to prevent lagging behind in their general development, correct existing defects and ensure their comprehensive development. In pedagogy, as a science of the laws of education, a wide range of phenomena is covered and the issues of organizing education in different conditions are developed. The science of pre-school deaf pedagogy develops based on the general laws of the science of pedagogy.

The scientific-methodological basis of deaf pedagogy for the school is philosophy, because philosophy determines the methodology of studying the goals and tasks of education, and provides an opportunity to approach the issue of education on a scientific basis. Didactics, which is the theory of information and education, belongs to the system of deaf pedagogy. Studying the nature, laws, principles and perspectives of education for hearing impaired children is part of the task of didactics. On this basis, the purpose, content, principles, methods, organizational forms and means of education are developed.

The science of surdopedagogy is based on the science of ethics in the development of didactic issues, for example, in the study of issues of moral education, in determining the goals, ways and methods of aesthetic education. The science of pre-school deaf pedagogy is directly related to general, pre-school and special psychology.

Psychology, as a science that studies the laws of mental development of a person in phylogenesis and ontogenesis, mental processes formed during the development, education and interaction of a person with the environment (perception, intuition, thinking, memory, imagination, feeling, will, etc.) studies. Using them, deaf pedagogy develops the content and methods of education of children with hearing impairment.

According to the scientific theories of psychologists L.S. Vygotsky, I.M. Solovev, T.V. Rozanova in the science of pre-school deaf pedagogy, if a deficiency in mental and physical development leads to a violation of the child's physical and mental development, such a child is considered anomalous. Hearing loss has a negative impact on the child's speech development: it prevents the development of speech as a means of communication, perception, thinking, cognitive development. In order to properly organize the pedagogical process in an educational institution, to

understand the general and specific aspects related to hearing loss, it is necessary to know the characteristics of the mental development of preschool children.

In the process of examining the hearing impaired, the possibilities of speech perception using a hearing aid are determined. At the first level of hearing loss, when the hearing loss does not exceed 50 db, the child is able to clearly perceive speech at a speaking height at a distance of 1-2 meters, and can engage in speech communication. At the second level of hearing loss, that is, when the hearing is reduced to 50-70 db, speech becomes difficult, since the speech is received from a distance of no more than 1 meter.

At the 3rd level of hearing loss, i.e. when the hearing loss exceeds 70 db, speech communication is impaired, because speech at the level of speech is vaguely perceived near the ear. It is known that when the hearing condition decreases by 15-20 db, there are difficulties in acquiring speech. L.V. Neumann considers this condition to be "the borderline condition of a normal hearing and a hearing impaired." According to L.V. Neumann's classification, the conditional boundary between hearing loss and deafness is within 85 db. When hearing loss is at the level of deafness, there will be no opportunity to learn speech independently (naturally).

Deaf children are divided into 4 groups depending on the frequency range of perceived sounds:

- 3- Group 1 - children who perceive the lowest frequency sounds (125-250 Hz). Group 2 - children who perceive frequencies up to 500 Hz.
- 4- Group 3 - children who perceive frequencies up to 1000 Hz.
- 5- Group 4 - children who perceive a wide range of frequencies, i.e. 2000 Hz and higher sound.

Deaf children with minimal residual hearing (groups 1-2) are able to perceive loud sounds from a close distance (shouting, the roar of a steam engine, the sound of a drum). Deaf children in groups 3-4 have more significant residual hearing, so they can perceive sounds of different frequencies from a small distance (various musical instruments and toys, loud cries of animals, some household sounds: bells, phone rings). , they can distinguish. Group 3-4 deaf children can distinguish several familiar words or syllables.

Thus, all deaf children have different amounts of residual hearing. Training on the development of special hearing abilities serves to recognize existing sounds and to develop oral speech

will help. Nowadays, the International classification indicators are used to assess the hearing condition in medical institutions. According to this classification, average hearing loss is determined at frequencies of 500, 1000, 2000 Hz.

1st level of hearing loss - hearing loss does not exceed 40 db. Level 2 hearing loss - hearing loss is between 40 db and 55 db. Level 3 hearing loss - hearing loss is between 55 db and 70 db. The 4th degree of hearing loss is represented by a decrease in hearing from 70 db to 90 db. If the hearing loss exceeds 90 db, this condition is defined as "deafness".

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